

Data on the area extent of other wooded land and of agroforestry systems globally, as extracted from major studies and as summarised by geographic region

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Summary

The area extent of other wooded land (*sensu* FAO, 2023) and of agroforestry systems globally has been assessed in different contexts using various methods, from individual country counts to regional and global satellite-based assessments. A summary of some major studies is provided in the below table. These data were compiled in order to allow a comparison of different studies, different geographic regions and different ecosystems. This was for the purpose of writing a contribution to the second report of the State of the World's Forest Genetic Resources (<https://www.fao.org/forest-genetic-resources/assessments/second-report/en/>) on the state of woodlands and agroforests.

As indicated in the footnotes of the table, regional comparisons are not straightforward because different studies have applied different regional groupings for countries. This argues for the application of standardised definitions of regions across future studies.

Table. Summary of data from some major studies on tree extent by geographic region, natural ecosystem and agricultural production system. Data are extracted from: the Global Forest Resources Assessment of 2020 (“FRA”) (FAO, 2020); the FAO-coordinated remote sensing survey carried out in parallel with FRA 2020 (“RSS”) (FAO, 2022); the FAO-coordinated drylands remote sensing survey (“Drylands RSS”) (FAO, 2019); and Zomer *et al.*’s (2014) agroforestry survey (“Zomer”). OWL = other wooded land. Mha = million ha.

Region	FRA OWL (Mha, to 2020)	RSS OWL (Mha, to 2018)	Drylands RSS ^A OWL in drylands (total, Mha, to 2015) ^B	Drylands RSS grassland with shrubs within OWL in drylands (Mha, to 2015)	Drylands RSS grassland with trees and shrubs within OWL in drylands (Mha, to 2015)	FRA agroforestry (Mha, to 2020, for 71 countries) ^C . Number of reporting countries in ()	RSS cropland with >10% tree cover (Mha, to 2018, includes oil palm)	RSS grassland with >10% tree cover (Mha, to 2018)	RSS cropland + grassland with >10% tree cover (Mha, to 2018)	Zomer agricultural land with >10% tree cover (= “agroforestry”, Mha, average 2008–2010). In (), in % terms, is the proportion of all agricultural land with >10% tree cover (a, average 2000–2002; b, average 2008–2010; b minus a ^D)
North and Central America and the Caribbean ^{E, F}	90.5	341	156.3	110.3	43.1	1.3 (14)	35.1	91.6	126.7	113.7 (46.6; 48.6; 2.0)
South America	146.6	191	52.4	40.2	10.5	0.1 (5)	22.5	133.2	155.7	255.2 (53.0; 65.6; 12.6)
Europe	100.5	183	10.6	4.2	4.7	0.1 (20)	46.0	92.1	138.1	103.5 (45.0; 45.0; 0)
North Africa ^G	59.1	39	10.3	3.9	5.5	0.2 (3)	27.1	28.3	55.4	NA ^H
Western and Central Africa	101.9	117	60.9	19.9	26.7	11.2 (6)	124.3	65.8	190.1	NA ^I

Region	FRA OWL (Mha, to 2020)	RSS OWL (Mha, to 2018)	Drylands RSS ^A OWL in drylands (total, Mha, to 2015) ^B	Drylands RSS grassland with shrubs within OWL in drylands (Mha, to 2015)	Drylands RSS grassland with trees and shrubs within OWL in drylands (Mha, to 2015)	FRA agroforestry (Mha, to 2020, for 71 countries) ^C . Number of reporting countries in (I)	RSS cropland with >10% tree cover (Mha, to 2018, includes oil palm)	RSS grassland with >10% tree cover (Mha, to 2018)	RSS cropland + grassland with >10% tree cover (Mha, to 2018)	Zomer agricultural land with >10% tree cover (= "agroforestry", Mha, average 2008–2010). In (I), in % terms, is the proportion of all agricultural land with >10% tree cover (a, average 2000–2002; b, average 2008–2010; b minus a ^D)
Eastern and Southern Africa ^J	284.4	252	128.8	61.2	61.5	1.4 (5)	66.4	105.6	172.0	NA ^K
Africa total ^{L, M}	445.5	407	200.0	85.0	93.7	12.8 (14)	217.7	199.7	417.4	120.8 (28.6; 30.5; 1.9)
Asia ^{N, O}	191.0	208	31.9	10.5	13.3	31.2 (16)	205.4	31.2	236.6	330.4 (40.2; 42.6; 2.4)
Oceania ^P	2.5	370	130.3	64.4	64.0	Negligible (2)	6.6	29.3	35.9	26.3 (30.3; 33.3; 3.0)

Table footnotes

A. The drylands remote sensing survey omitted from calculations large areas of “presumed drylands” in South America, Southern Africa and Central Asia that are on the “wetter” end of the drylands spectrum.

B. Sum of sub-categories tabulated in the report.

C. These numbers are given for completeness, but many countries where agroforestry is a major land use did not report, or did not fully report, figures to the Global Forest Resources Assessment of 2020.

D. Where required, percent changes take account of relative area contributions of regions as initially reported by Zomer *et al.* (2014) that are pooled for current reporting.

E. Data for “North America”, “Central America” and “Caribbean” were (also) given separately in some reports, but summed data are used for current reporting to allow comparison with other studies.

F. For Zomer *et al.* (2014) the value given is the sum of the reported regions of “North America” and “Central America”.

G. Termed “Northern Africa” in the drylands remote sensing survey and the Global Forest Resources Assessment of 2020.

H. “North Africa” and “Western Asia” are reported as a joint figure by Zomer *et al.* (2014). These data had to be excluded in the current compilation as they are not comparable with categories applied in other reports.

I. Data only reported for “Sub-Saharan Africa” as a single region by Zomer *et al.* (2014).

J. “Eastern Africa” and “Southern Africa” were considered separately in the drylands remote sensing survey, but were grouped for current reporting to allow comparison with other studies.

K. Data only reported for “Sub-Saharan Africa” as a single region by Zomer *et al.* (2014).

L. For the case of the drylands remote sensing survey, the figure reported in the current compilation is the sum of Africa’s several individual regions’ values (no final sum given for Africa as a whole in the report).

M. For Zomer *et al.* (2014) the value given is for the region “Sub-Saharan Africa” only (i.e. excluding “North Africa” – see earlier table footnote).

N. “Asia” was divided into separate regions in a number of studies, but the country groupings within the regions were not always the same. For current purposes, data were therefore summarised only at the continental level. For the case of the drylands remote

sensing survey, the figure reported is the sum of Asia's individual regions' values (no final sum given for Asia as a whole in the report).

O. For Zomer *et al.* (2014) the value given is for the sum of the individual regional values within Asia but excludes "Western Asia" (see earlier table footnote).

P. Australia did not report under the category of OWL for the Global Forest Resources Assessment of 2020.

References

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